

Evaluation of the Policy of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT) in Poverty Alleviation in Gorontalo City

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Nov 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Dec 2024; **Published:** 28 Jan 2025

Abstract: The purpose of this study was to determine and describe (1) effectiveness, (2) efficiency, (3) adequacy, (4) equity, (5) responsiveness and (6) accuracy of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program in Poverty Alleviation in Gorontalo City. This study uses a qualitative research method and for data collection the researcher combines interviews, documentation and observation. To analyze the data, the researcher uses the opinions of Miles and Huberman, namely data reduction, data display and conclusions. The results of the study indicate that (1) Effectiveness shows that the BPNT program is quite effective in helping them in lightening the burden of life even though it does not have a very large impact and the assistance provided has helped beneficiary families (KPM) in meeting balanced nutrition; (2) Efficiency shows that in this Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program it is quite easy for the community, beneficiaries can directly take it using KKS through the distributing bank or ATM or the distributing post and through e-warong; (3) Adequacy shows that the BPNT program can help meet the food needs of the recipient community, but it is not enough until the distribution time of the following month; (4) Equity shows that this program is considered not entirely fair, because there is inequality in the screening of prospective BPNT assistance recipients, there are findings that some beneficiaries do not come from the category of extreme poor people, so that the distribution of assistance is considered less even; (5) Responsiveness shows that the government's response to the needs of the poor through the BPNT program is quite good but there are still poor people who have not been touched by BPNT assistance; (6) Accuracy shows that the policy that allows beneficiaries of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program to withdraw assistance in cash has had a negative impact on the main objectives of the program, this can be seen from the misuse of this assistance to pay debts, buy alcoholic beverages and even gamble. So this shows the potential for problems in changing the implementation of the policy.

Keywords: Evaluation, Policy, Poverty, BPNT Program.

I. INTRODUCTION

Development in a country is essentially an effort aimed at changing every aspect of the country's life from the existing conditions towards a better future. One of the developments being carried out by the government, especially developing countries, is the problem of poverty alleviation. Poverty is a serious problem that is still being experienced by Asian countries such as Indonesia. One of the ways the government has done to overcome this is the Gorontalo City Government has implemented a BPNT Program to overcome poverty. The government has begun to perfect the BPNT program which is assistance issued by the government to help the poor in the food sector such as rice, eggs and other basic necessities.

This can be seen in table 1. regarding the number of BPNT recipients from 2019-2024 as follows:

Table 1. Percentage of Number of BPNT Recipients in Gorontalo City 2019-2023

Number of BPNT Recipients in Gorontalo City	
Year	Number of BPNT Recipients
2019	7,157 souls
2020	11,403 souls
2021	10,233 Souls
2022	13,587 souls
2023	13,244 souls
2024	13,065 souls

Source: Gorontalo City Social Service, 2024

Based on data on the number of BPNT recipients in Gorontalo City from 2019-2023, there has often been an increase. This is because the BPNT program with the basic food program is a program issued by the government whose purpose is to help poor households to meet their food needs. During the pandemic, in order to improve food security and nutrition for the poor, items that can be exchanged are not only rice and eggs but also for other sources of carbohydrates, protein and vitamins such as nuts, vegetables, fruits, chicken and others as long as they are in accordance with the amount of assistance distributed by the government. The amount of Non-Cash Pagan Assistance (BPNT) is IDR 110,000 / KPM / month, in January - February 2020 it became IDR 150,000 / KPM / month which then became IDR. 200,000,-/kpm/month starting in March 2020. The distribution of non-cash food assistance itself uses the E-warong feature which is spread in many places, currently the distribution in Gorontalo City is getting wider and will increase from year to year. This assistance distribution system is given to Beneficiary Families (KPM) who have a Prosperous Family Card (KKS) which is used as evidence or transaction to exchange or obtain food assistance according to the amount of assistance that has been given. The implementation of a policy or a program certainly cannot be separated from what is called evaluation, where this evaluation is an improvement or controller in the implementation of the program. Evaluation as a benchmark used to provide assessments to the government and stakeholders as policy makers or programs. In evaluation there are criteria for testing a policy or program. To be able to assess the success of the program, researchers carry out evaluations using policy evaluation criteria which are divided into 6 types of policy evaluation criteria, namely (1) effectiveness, (2) efficiency, (3) adequacy, (4) equity, (5) responsiveness, (6) accuracy [1].

Based on the conditions that have been described, the objectives of this research are (1) To find out and describe how Effective the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program is in Poverty Alleviation in Gorontalo City; (2) To find out and describe how Efficient the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program is in Poverty Alleviation in Gorontalo City; (3) To find out and describe how the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program is in Poverty Alleviation in Gorontalo City; (4) To find out and describe how the Distribution of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program is in Poverty Alleviation in Gorontalo City; (5) To find out and describe how the Responsiveness of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program is in Poverty Alleviation in Gorontalo City; (6) To find out and describe how the Accuracy of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program is in Poverty Alleviation in Gorontalo City.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Administration

Policy is an important instrument that can be a driver of organizational transformation [2]. Public policy is a program created by the government in a country that is intended to address all issues or problems that exist in the midst of society, both those that have been implemented and those that are still being planned. Basically, public policy is initiated by the government to improve the welfare of society. In every policy-making, the government must refer to society because the object of public policy is the interests of society [3]. Public policy is decisions made by someone who has authority in government, both formal and informal.

There are so many definitions of public policy. Public policy according to Dye is defined as whatever governments choose to do or not to do (public policy whatever governments choose to do or not to do)" [4]. The concept is very broad because public policy includes something that is not done by the government in addition to what the government does when the government faces a public problem. For example, when the government knows that there is a damaged highway and it does not make a policy to fix it, it means that the government has taken a policy. Dye's definition of public policy contains the meaning that (1) public policy is made by a government agency, not a private organization; (2) public policy concerns choices that must be made or not made by a government agency. The government's policy not to create a new program or to remain on the status quo, for example not paying taxes is a public policy.

Policy Evaluation

Evaluation can also be seen as an assessment or improvement of the performance of a program that is being implemented, and the results of the evaluation can then be used to determine whether a program or policy can be beneficial or not for the target community, at what point the policy can be continued, improved, or even stopped [5]. [6] Evaluation is a procedure to provide details on the extent to which a particular activity has been achieved, how the difference in achievement from a certain standard to determine whether there is a difference between the two, and how the benefits that have been achieved when compared with the expected and obtained results [7]

This is in line with Dye's opinion regarding public policy, which states that public policy is whatever the government chooses to do or carry out [8].

Policy Evaluation Models

The following are policy evaluation models, including the following.

1. Briekerhoff Model

Briekerhoff put forward three groups of evaluations, namely [9]:

- a. *Fixed and Emergent Evaluation*, which relates to the continuity or development of evaluation approaches, evaluation problems and criteria and how far they are ultimately met;
- b. *Formative vs summative evaluation*, which relates to the need for and usefulness of evaluation;
- c. *Experimental and quasi Experimental Design vs Natural/Unobtrusive Inquiry*, which is related to the process of intervention, manipulation.

2. Stake Model or Countenance Model

Emphasizing two evaluation bases, namely description and judgment and the existence of each program stage, namely [10]: Antecedents (context), Transaction (process) Outcomes (output). In addition, he emphasized the importance of relative comparisons (between one program and another) and negative comparisons (between the program offered and the one that has been standardized).

3. Program Evaluation Model According to Nagarajan

Program evaluation is a system consisting of the main elements, namely analysis of needs, objectives, input, program implementation (activities) [11]. Output/results (output) and impact (outcome). The scope of program evaluation includes evaluation of implementation, objectives, resources, activities or program implementation, results or output, impact or outcome, evaluation of program relevance, program efficiency, cost-benefit evaluation, evaluation of effectiveness 1, evaluation of effectiveness 2, evaluation of adequacy, evaluation of appropriateness or is a logical thought that shows the relationship between input, activities, output and outcome.

4. Responsive Evaluation Model

Wirawan stated that this evaluation model was developed by Stake. This model is the face of the evaluation, the overall picture or the evaluation landscape, not just measuring the objectives [12]. Evaluation is said to be responsive if it meets three criteria, namely (1) more directly oriented to program activities than program objectives; (2) responding to the information needs of the audience; and (3) the perspectives of different values from the people served are reported in the success and failure of the program. From this statement, it means that this evaluation is oriented to program activities. Responsive evaluation focuses primarily on issues and problems that are of primary concern to stakeholders. This approach strives to develop technology to be able to improve and focus the natural behavior of an evaluator.

5. CSE-UCLA Evaluation Model (Center for the Study of Evaluation- University of California in Los Angeles Evaluation Model)

Tayib Napis stated that the CSE-UCLA evaluation model developed by Alkin has five evaluation stages [12], including 1) System assessment, which is an evaluation that provides information about the state or position of the system, 2) Program planning, which is an evaluation that helps select certain programs that may be successful in meeting program needs, 3) Program implementation, which is an evaluation that provides information on whether the program has been introduced to the right group as planned, 4) Program improvement, which is an evaluation that provides information on how the program functions, works or runs, whether it is heading towards a certain achievement, 5) Program certification, which provides information on the value or usefulness of the program. The CSE-UCLA evaluation model is an evaluation model that is suitable for evaluating service programs that help human life.

6. CIPP Evaluation Model (Context, Input, Process, Product Evaluation Model)

The advantage of the CIPP Evaluation Model [13] is that it is more comprehensive than other evaluation models because the object of evaluation is not only the results but also includes context, input, process, and results. The CIPP Evaluation Model (Context, Input, Process, Product) [14] is one of the most frequently used evaluation models in program evaluation. This model was developed by Stufflebeam and Shinkfield in 1985 and has undergone several revisions since then. The four main components, CIPP evaluation can be carried out in four stages, namely context evaluation, input evaluation, process evaluation, and product evaluation. Evaluation can be carried out sequentially or simultaneously, depending on the needs and objectives of the evaluation.

7. Discrepancy Evaluation Model

Wirawan explained that gap evaluation requires six steps in its implementation (Divayana 2018), namely (a) developing a design and standard; (b) planning an evaluation using a discrepancy evaluation model; (c) capturing the performance of the evaluation object; (d) identifying discrepancies between standards and the implementation of the results of the

evaluation object; (e) determining the cause of the discrepancy between standards and the performance of the evaluation object; (f) eliminating the discrepancy by making changes to the implementation of the evaluation object.

8. Ucla Model

Alkin conveyed five types of evaluation [15], namely:

- a. *System Assessment*, which relates to the state or position of the system;
- b. *Program Planning*, assisting in program selection;
- c. *Program Implementation*, which provides information on how far the program has been introduced;
- d. *Improvement Program*, namely providing information about how far the program has functioned and been implemented;
- e. *Certification Program*, which provides information about the value or utility of an activity.

9. Ernest R House Model

Ernest R House created a quite different evaluation taxonomy, which divides evaluation models into [16]:

- a. System Model, with main indicators of efficiency
- b. Behavioral Model, with the main indicators being productivity and accountability
- c. Decision formulation model, with the main indicators being choice of use and social benefits
- d. Goal free model with main indicators being choice of use and social benefits.
- e. The critical art model (art criticism) with the main indicators being increasingly better standards and increasing awareness.
- f. Professional review model, with the main indicator being resolution
- g. Case study model, with the main indicator being understanding of diversity.

There is also a selection of evaluations according to the evaluation technique, namely:

- a. Comparative Evaluation, namely comparing policy implementation (process and results) with the same or different implementation, in the same or different place.
- b. Historical Evaluation, namely making policy evaluations based on the historical span of the emergence of these policies.
- c. Laboratory or experimental evaluation, namely evaluation but using experiments placed in a kind of laboratory.
- d. There is a hock evaluation, namely an evaluation that is carried out suddenly in a short time to get a picture at that time (snap shot)

10. Jones Model

In general, policy evaluation is an activity that involves estimating or assessing policies, their substance, implementation and impact. Basically, policy evaluation is carried out for 3 purposes [17], namely:

- a. *Political evaluation*(political evaluation). Conducted to see whether the program provides benefits to the country. Can this be interpreted to open up opportunities for re-election, to gain media support, or to gain campaign donations.

- b. *Organizational evaluation*(organizational evaluation). This evaluation is conducted to obtain answers about whether the policies or programs implemented generate support for implementing agencies. Whether the benefits to these agencies exceed the costs incurred. Whether the policies implemented lead to further expansion for these agencies.
- c. *Substantive evaluation*(substantive or real evaluation). This is an evaluation conducted to see whether the policy or program implemented has achieved the objectives that have been set both legally and in the details of the policy that is to be achieved next, and what the impact of the policy or program is on the targeted problem.

11. William N. Dunn's Policy Evaluation Model

According to Dunn later, evaluation plays a number of main functions in policy analysis [18], namely as follows:

- a. Evaluation provides valid and reliable information about policy performance, namely about the extent to which needs, values and opportunities have been achieved through public action. In this case, evaluation reveals the extent to which certain goals (e.g. health improvement) and certain targets have been achieved.
- b. Evaluation contributes to the clarification and critique of the values underlying goals and targets. Values are clarified by defining and operationalizing goals and targets. Values are also critiqued by systematically questioning the appropriateness of goals and targets in relation to the problem at hand. In questioning the appropriateness of goals and targets, the analyst can examine alternative sources of values (interest groups, civil servants, and client groups) as well as their basis in various forms of rationality (technical, economic, legal, social, and substantive).
- c. Evaluation contributes to the application of other policy analysis methods, especially for "problem formulation" and "recommendation". Information about the adequacy or inadequacy of policy performance can contribute to the reformulation of policy problems. By indicating that goals and targets need to be defined. Evaluation can also contribute to the definition of new policy alternatives or policy revisions by indicating that previously favored policy alternatives need to be discarded and replaced by others.

Non-Cash Food Assistance Program Policy

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Social Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2019 concerning the Distribution of Non-Cash Food Assistance, Article 1 Paragraph (4) Non-Cash Food Assistance, hereinafter abbreviated as BPNT, is social assistance distributed in a non-cash manner from the Government which is given to KPM every month through electronic money which is then used to purchase food that has been determined at E-Warong. BPNT is food assistance from the government which is given to KPM (Beneficiary Families) every month through an Electronic Account Mechanism which is used only to purchase food at e-Warong KUBE PKH/food traders who work together with the Distributing Bank [19]

According to the BPNT manual, namely BPNT is a government policy program in the form of non-cash or food assistance distributed to poor people who meet the requirements for Non-Cash Food Assistance recipients through combo cards in collaboration with E-warong. Recipients of BPNT assistance are also called KPM (beneficiary families). KPM are families registered in the list of beneficiaries and selected by the Ministry of Social Affairs and have the lowest socio-economic conditions in the implementation area.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

In collecting data on the BPNT Program in Overcoming Poverty in Gorontalo City, the researcher used a qualitative research method with a descriptive approach. By using qualitative research, researchers can recognize objects and feel what subjects experience in

everyday life [20]. In this article, the researcher describes and analyzes phenomena related to the Evaluation of the BPNT Program in Gorontalo City.

Data collection using direct observation, interview, and documentation methods. In this study, researchers conducted in-depth interviews with informants, then observation and documentation by reviewing data, references and laws and regulations used to maintain scientific truth. Interviews involve direct interaction between researchers and informants to obtain data in the form of views, experiences, and perceptions. Observation involves direct observation, documentation studies involve collecting data from documents, archives, or other written materials [21].

The data analysis technique used in this article after the data is collected begins with reducing the data, presenting the data and then drawing conclusions. Furthermore, the results of the reduction are processed in such a way that they appear intact and then conclusions and verification will be carried out [21]. This article uses data validity techniques because they are considered important. So that the research results are not doubted as scientific work, the research data must be tested with the following instruments: (1) Credibility Test, (2) Testing *Transfability*, (3) Dependability Testing, (4) Confirmability Testing.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study concerning the Evaluation of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program Policy in overcoming poverty in Gorontalo City based on the Policy Evaluation according to William Dunn (2003) are as follows:

1. Effectiveness of Non-Cash Assistance Program (BPNT) Policy in Gorontalo City

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the BPNT program is quite effective in helping them ease the burden of life even though it does not have a very big impact and the assistance provided has helped beneficiary families (KPM) in meeting balanced nutrition. In seeing the level of effectiveness of BPNT in Gorontalo City, there are 4 study targets used, namely according to Maijun & Utama (2013) as a basis for knowledge whether the program has run as expected, namely the accuracy of program targets, program socialization, program objectives, and program monitoring.

The statement above shows that the effectiveness of the BPNT program is still not in accordance with Damanik & Marom's theory regarding the fulfillment of effectiveness criteria, so it can be concluded that that the BPNT program in Gorontalo City was quite effective in achieving its goals, although there were several operational constraints that hampered the smooth running of the program, such as delays in distribution and inaccurate data on beneficiaries [22]. This means that effectiveness can be achieved if a program in its implementation has achieved its goals with the right targets and provided beneficial value.

Based on the theory above, it can be concluded that the effectiveness element of the BPNT program can be said to be quite good. This can be seen in its implementation that this assistance has been able to help KPM Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT) but this assistance has not been fully received by the poor who are the targets of the program as stated in the program objectives in the regulations which is caused by the updating of beneficiary family data which still needs to be improved so that this assistance can be comprehensive for the poor or those whose lives are not decent and people who experience social problems.

2. Efficiency of Non-Cash Assistance Program (BPNT) Policy in Gorontalo City

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program is quite easy for the community, recipients of assistance benefits can directly take it using KKS through the distributing bank or ATM or distribution post and through e-warong. To see the level of efficiency of BPNT in Gorontalo City, there are 2 (two) study targets used, namely according to Rusydiana (2018) there are two things that are the targets of the study, namely

resource efficiency and time efficiency. The BPNT program uses quite a lot of human resources needed in monitoring and distributing assistance starting from the Social Service, the Gorontalo City Food Social Assistance Coordination Team, Social Companions from the Sub-district Social Welfare Workers (TKSK), and BPNT distribution agents.

The statement above shows that the efficiency of the BPNT program is in accordance with Rusydiana's theory, namely the fulfillment of human resources and it can be concluded that the BPNT program is relatively efficient in using available resources, although there are still several challenges related to waiting times in aid distribution [23]. This means that efficiency refers to the efforts made by a program, whether by implementing a policy or program, in achieving the goals that have been set by using resources in the form of costs, time, and energy required in its implementation.

Based on the theory above, it can be concluded that the distribution flow of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT) has a shorter distribution mechanism so that KPM can directly take it using KKS through the distributing bank or ATM or distributing post and through e-warong. The Social Service has collaborated with Bank BRI as the distributing bank and PT Pos as the distributing post. With this collaboration as a distributing bank, Bank BRI provides the Prosperous Family Card (KKS). Then from the distributing post it also provides it in cash for KPM of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT). However, the distribution process through PT Pos takes longer because KPM has to queue and even KPM requires transportation costs to go to the Post Office so that distribution through KKS is considered more efficient than through PT Pos.

3. Adequacy of Non-Cash Assistance Program (BPNT) Policy in Gorontalo City

Based on the results of the study, it shows that the BPNT program can help meet the food needs of recipient communities. However, this only provides limited benefits because the assistance received is not enough until the distribution time of the following month, namely the assistance provided can only be used to meet food needs for 1 to 2 weeks. In other words, this program is not enough to solve the problems that exist in the community. In addition, this BPNT program can change the attitudes, behavior, and mindset of the community.

The previous statement can be seen that the adequacy of the BPNT program is still not in accordance with the theory of Damanik & Marom (2016) namely that the community's problems regarding the large amount of expenditure in meeting the food needs of Beneficiary Families have not been resolved [22]. This means that adequacy is seen from the assessment related to the achievement of goals or desired results of a policy or program that can solve the problems that are occurring. Basically, the purpose of the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT) is to help the poor in meeting their food needs, meaning that the Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT) must be able to help meet the food needs of all poor people and guarantee this even though this assistance is only partial.

Based on the theory above, it can be concluded that the assistance provided is considered not to fully meet the basic food needs of the poor. Most beneficiary families (KPM) stated that the nominal assistance was not enough to meet food needs for one month, so additional personal expenses were still needed to meet the family's nutritional needs.

4. Equalization of Non-Cash Assistance Program (BPNT) Policy in Gorontalo City

Based on the research results, it was shown that this program was considered not entirely fair, because there was inequality in the screening of prospective recipients of BPNT assistance, there were findings that some beneficiaries did not come from the category of extremely poor people, so that the distribution of assistance was considered uneven, this can be seen from several obstacles, such as there are still families who are not registered in the DTKS because they do not have official documents or experience administrative difficulties. Sometimes there are also rapid changes in economic status, for example people who were

previously not included in the poor category, suddenly become poor because they lose their jobs or other reasons. Things like this sometimes make social workers have to continue to update the data of aid recipients and try their best so that the distribution of BPNT can be right on target and no one feels neglected or does not meet the poverty criteria.

To see the level of BPNT distribution in Gorontalo City, it can be seen from the 2 (two) study targets used in this study, namely the distribution of BPNT and the reduction of poor people [24]. This means that the dimension of distribution is seen from the implementation of the program whether it can run evenly both in terms of implementation and the benefits obtained fairly. KPM Non-Cash Food Assistance Program (BPNT) as beneficiaries must be able to know about the objectives of the program implementation and in general KPM already knows the objectives of this assistance.

Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that the inequality in access to screening of prospective beneficiaries reflects weaknesses in the data verification and validation system, although in this case the government has attempted to ensure the accuracy of BPNT recipient data through data verification in the DTKS. However, in several sub-districts, data entry errors were still found which caused some people who were entitled to receive assistance not to be registered. In addition, there are also families who no longer meet the requirements but are still registered as recipients of assistance. Efforts to improve and update data periodically need to be increased so that the distribution of assistance is more even.

5. Responsiveness of Non-Cash Assistance Program (BPNT) Policy in Gorontalo City

Based on the results of this study, it shows that the government's response to the needs of the poor through the BPNT program is quite good. However, there are still complaints from the community regarding the quality of food provided in several e-warungs and there are still poor people who complain about the targets for receiving BPNT which are not yet appropriate where there are still people who have not been touched by BPNT assistance since the beginning of the BPNT program so that the government needs to be more responsive in responding to this and ensuring the quality and quantity of food provided in accordance with the standards that have been set.

To see the level of BPNT in Gorontalo City, it can be seen from the study targets used in this study, namely the response of the target group regarding the fulfillment of BPNT for their needs and vulnerable and affected groups get preference (priority) for the BPNT program [25]. This means that this responsiveness leads to the program's ability to provide responses related to changes or community needs quickly and effectively. Responsiveness is important because community conditions change with different needs, for that the response from the community as beneficiaries is something that is needed for policy and program implementers. In addition, the response from program implementers is also something that is needed.

Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that public complaints about the BPNT program are seen from the target of BPNT recipients that have not been appropriate where there are still people who have not been touched by this BPNT assistance since the beginning of the BPNT program so that the Government needs to be more responsive in responding to this and ensuring the quality and quantity of food provided in accordance with the standards that have been set. This Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) Program is assistance related to the fulfillment of KPM food. However, from the program implementers, it can be seen that this food need has not increased in other words it still looks the same or as usual because this assistance is only temporary and helps to buy some of the recipient's food needs.

6. The Accuracy of the Non-Cash Assistance Program (BPNT) Policy in Gorontalo City

Based on the results of the study which showed that when assistance can be withdrawn in cash without supervision, the main objective of the program, which is to provide food needs, is neglected. Cash withdrawals provide too much freedom to beneficiaries, which are not

always used for basic needs. In some cases, family members or other parties can take over the use of assistance funds for personal interests that are not relevant to the objectives of the program. KPM misuses the use of this assistance to pay off motorbikes, pay debts, buy alcohol and even gamble. So this shows the potential for problems in the implementation of the policy.

From the statement above, it can be seen that the responsibility of the BPNT program is in accordance with Lejiu's theory, namely that the results of BPNT are beneficial and the contents of existing regulations are in accordance with the reality in the field. This means that the dimension of accuracy can be analyzed by looking at the results that have been obtained with their suitability to the benefits resulting from the implementation of a policy or program [26].

Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that the policy that allows beneficiaries of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program to withdraw assistance in cash has had a negative impact on the main objectives of the program, namely meeting food needs and overcoming poverty. The misuse of aid funds for inappropriate things, such as buying alcohol, gambling, or paying installments, indicates potential problems in the implementation of the policy, for which a re-evaluation is needed, because it is contrary to the main objectives of the program in overcoming poverty and improving food welfare. The government must ensure that the aid program runs in a controlled manner and provides a sustainable positive impact on the beneficiary community.

V. CLOSING

Based on the findings and discussion of the research that has been conducted, answers to the problems presented have been found, so it can be concluded that (1) Effectiveness shows that the BPNT program is quite effective in helping them to ease the burden of life even though it does not have a very large impact and the assistance provided has helped beneficiary families (KPM) in meeting balanced nutrition; (2) Efficiency shows that in this Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program, it is quite easy for the community, beneficiaries can directly take it using KKS through the distributing bank or ATM or distributing post and through e-warong; (3) Adequacy shows that the BPNT program can help meet the food needs of the recipient community, but it is not enough until the distribution time of the following month; (4) Equity shows that this program is considered not entirely fair, because there is an imbalance in the screening of prospective BPNT assistance recipients, there are findings that some beneficiaries do not come from the category of extreme poor people, so that the distribution of assistance is considered less even; (5) Responsiveness shows that the government's response to the needs of the poor through the BPNT program is quite good but there are still poor people who have not been touched by BPNT assistance; (6) accuracy shows that the policy that allows beneficiaries of the Non-Cash Food Assistance (BPNT) program to withdraw assistance in cash has had a negative impact on the main objectives of the program, as seen in the misuse of this assistance to pay off motorbikes, pay debts, buy alcoholic beverages and even gamble. So this shows that there is potential for problems in the implementation of this policy.

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